

Antispasmodics Derived from Hydroxyflavones

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β -Diethylaminoacetoxy, β -aminoethoxy, and β -diethylaminoethoxy derivatives have been prepared from hydroxyflavones. Some of them have been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic properties and found to possess activities comparable to standard compounds now used in practice.

In the present investigation the following derivatives of flavones have been prepared: (i) β -diethylaminoacetoxy-, (ii) β -aminoethoxy-, (iii) β -diethylaminoethoxy-.

For preparing the compounds of type (i), hydroxyflavones were condensed with chloroacetyl chloride and the resulting products were made to react with diethylamine under appropriate conditions. Compounds of type (ii) were prepared by condensing hydroxyflavones with β -bromoethylamine hydrobromide. Compounds of type (iii) were prepared by condensing hydroxyflavones with diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride.

The following hydroxyflavones were used for the purpose: (1) 6-hydroxy-, (2) 7-hydroxy-, (3) 6-chloro-2'-hydroxy-, (4) 8-chloro-2'-hydroxy-, (5) 8-bromo-7-hydroxy-, (6) 6,8-dinitro-7-hydroxy-, (7) 6-chloro-4'-hydroxy-.

The compounds No. 3 to 7 were prepared from the corresponding chalcones by refluxing with amyl alcohol and an equal amount of selenium dioxide in an oil bath at 145-50° for 12 hr. The details of preparation are recorded in the Experimental.

The chalcones were prepared by condensing hydroxyacetophenones in cold with aldehydes in molar quantities in aldehyde-free ethanol in presence of a 50% solution of sodium hydroxide (twice the weight of ketone taken).

7-Hydroxy- and 6-hydroxy-flavones were prepared from resacetophenone and quinaacetophenone respectively by benzoylation and ring-closure with aqueous potassium carbonate.

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Chloro-2'-hydroxyflavone.—3'-Chloro-2,2'-dihydroxychalcone (2 g.), selenium dioxide (2 g.), and amyl alcohol (20 ml) were refluxed in an oil bath at 145°-50° for 12 hours. The flask was cooled and the contents were filtered to remove selenium. The residue containing selenium was washed two or three times with 15 ml of ethyl ether. The filtrate and the washings were combined and all the ether and amyl alcohol were removed by steam distillation, leaving an oily brown substance as residue, which was cooled and crystallised from acetone; m. p. 233°, yield 41%. (Found: C, 65.86; H, 3.21. $C_{15}H_9O_3$ requires C, 65.93; H, 3.29%).

The analytical data and m.p. of other hydroxyflavones, prepared from their corresponding chalcones in a similar manner, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Flavones.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	6-Chloro-2'-hydroxy-	187°	34	65.75	65.93	3.18	3.29
2	8-Chloro-2'-hydroxy-	233°	41	65.86	65.93	3.21	3.29
3	8-Bromo-7-hydroxy-	223°	28	56.71	56.78	2.72	2.83
4	6,8-Dinitro-7-hydroxy-	248°	43	54.28	54.54	2.68	2.72
5	6-Chloro-4'-hydroxy-	223°	35	65.79	65.93	3.01	3.29

7-Diethylaminoacetoxyflavone.—This involved the preparation of the intermediate, 7-chloroacetoxyflavone, which was prepared as follows.

To 7-hydroxyflavone (1.2 g.), dissolved in 15 ml of dry benzene mixed with a little pyridine in a r.b. flask, chloroacetyl chloride (2.3 g.) was added (the latter may be added in excess). The whole solution was refluxed on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. at 70°. After distilling benzene, the residue was added to a large volume of water. The solid separating was washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 241° (decomp.), yield 60%. (Found : Cl, 11.11. $C_{17}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 11.25%).

The analytical data and m.p. of chloroacetoxy derivatives of other hydroxyflavones, prepared as above, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Chloroacetoxyflavones

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	7-R-F*	241°(d)	60	11.11	11.25
2	6-R-F	251°(d)	55	11.19	11.25
3	6-Chloro-2'-R-F	239°	40	19.97	20.28
4	8-Chloro-2'-R-F	235°(d)	43	20.03	20.28
5	8-Bromo-7-R-F	237°(d)	25	8.69	8.99
6	6,8-Dinitro-7-R-F	> 250°	33	8.43	8.54
7	6-Chloro-4'-R-F	219°	45	20.17	20.28

* F denotes flavone.

(d) denotes decomposition.

To 7-chloroacetoxyflavone (1.6 g.) diethylamine (0.6 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 6 to 8 hr. Diethylamine (each time about 0.5 g.) was added two or three times in course of heating. The reaction product was first washed with a very dilute solution of HCl and then with water and was finally crystallised from benzene; m.p. 208°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 71.68; H, 5.39; N, 3.88. $C_{21}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 71.79; H, 5.98; N, 3.98%).

The analytical data and m.p. of diethylaminoacetoxy derivatives of other hydroxyflavones, prepared similarly, are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Diethylaminoacetoxyflavones.

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	7-R-F*	208°	65	3.88	3.98
2	6-R-F	233°(d)	50	3.93	3.98
3	6-Chloro-2'-R-F	239°	45	3.59	3.63
4	8-Chloro-2'-R-F	241°	45	3.60	3.63
5	8-Bromo-7-R-F	> 250°	25	3.19	3.25
6	6,8-Dinitro-7-R-F	> 250°	30	9.17	9.52
7	6-Chloro-4'-R-F	255°	35	3.59	3.63

7-Aminoethoxyflavones.—To acetone (15 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in a dry conical flask β -bromoethylamine hydrobromide (4.1g.) was added and the contents were thoroughly mixed. 7-Hydroxyflavone (2.4 g.) was then added with shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. Acetone was evaporated and water was added to the residue after cooling. It was kept overnight when the residue solidified. After filtration, the residue was again washed with water two or three times and then crystallised from ethanol; m.p. > 250°, yield 55%. (Found: C, 72.39; H, 5.31; N, 4.93. C₁₇H₁₅O₃N requires C, 72.59; H, 5.33; N, 4.98%).

The analytical data and m.p. of the β -aminoethoxy derivatives of other hydroxyflavones, prepared in a similar manner, are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	7-R-F*	> 250°	55	4.93	4.98
2	6-R-F	236°(d)	55	4.89	4.98
3	6-Chloro 2'-R-F	230°	40	4.39	4.43
4	8-Chloro 2'-R-F	239°	45	4.40	4.43
5	8-Bromo-7-R-F	270°(d)	25	3.83	3.88
6	6,8-Dinitro-7-R-F	> 250°	26	11.01	11.32
7	6-Chloro-4'-R-F	198°	35	4.29	4.43

*F denotes flavone.

7- β -Diethylaminoethoxyflavones.—To acetone (15 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in a dry conical flask diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (2.6 g.) was added and the contents were thoroughly mixed. 7-Hydroxyflavone (2.4 g.) was then added with shaking. The reaction mixture was processed in the same way as the above flavone. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 73°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 74.21; H, 6.78; N, 4.04. C₂₁H₂₃O₃N requires C, 74.77; H, 6.82; N, 4.15%).

The analytical data and m.p. of β -diethylaminoethoxy derivatives of other hydroxyflavones, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	7-R-F	73°	50	4.04	4.15
2	6-R-F	49°	55	3.98	4.15
3	6-Chloro-2'-R-F	> 250°	35	3.75	3.76
4	8-Chloro-2'-R-F	216°	40	3.73	3.76
5	8-Bromo-7-R-F	> 250°	35	3.31	3.36
6	6,8-Dinitro-7-R-F.	> 250°	30	9.59	9.83
7	6-Chloro-4'-R-F	189°	35	3.71	3.76

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